

REPORT

A.2.2.2: Validation of the fitness of purpose of the performance assessment protocol developed in A2.1.4 by demonstrating its applicability for ammonia

As part of WP2 task 2.2, BiometCAP partners have demonstrated the fitness of purpose of the performance assessment protocol developed in Task 2.1 (specifically in A2.1.4) using the following validated methods: gas chromatography, spectroscopy and spectrometry analytical systems. The validation exercise is shown on the map below:

NPL and VSL will each validate the fitness of purpose of the performance assessment protocol developed in A2.1.4 by demonstrating its applicability for ammonia using non-dispersive Infrared (NDIR) (NPL) and laser spectroscopy (VSL). NPL will use the gravimetrically prepared static standards produced in A1.1.2 and the dynamic system from A1.2.1. VSL will use the dynamically prepared standards produced in A1.3.1. A short written report will be produced by NPL and VSL.

The two reports are gathered in this document.

REPORT

A2.2.2: Validation of the fitness of purpose of the performance assessment protocol developed in A2.1.4 by demonstrating its applicability for ammonia using GC-NCD with the static standards produced in A1.1.2.

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Contents

<u>Contents</u>	4
<u>1: Introduction</u>	5
<u>2: Reference standards</u>	5
<u>3: Experimental</u>	6
<u>4: Linearity</u>	8
<u>5: Trueness</u>	12
<u>6: Precision</u>	14
<u>6.1: Repeatability</u>	14
<u>6.2 Within-lab reproducibility (intermediate precision)</u>	15
<u>8: Limit of detection and quantification</u>	16
<u>9: Interferences/selectivity</u>	16
<u>10: Uncertainty Budget</u>	17
<u>11: Conclusion</u>	18

1: Introduction

The BiometCAP project addresses the need for SI-traceable validation of methods used in the conformity assessment of biomethane. This report describes the performance evaluation of the method, defined in A1.2.1, for quantification of ammonia in methane using a gas chromatograph with nitrogen chemiluminescence detector (GC-NCD).

2: Reference standards

The dynamic amount fractions used in method validation were generated through dilution of a ~20 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ ammonia in methane static reference material (D148951). This was prepared and validated in accordance with ISO 614201 and ISO 6143. All static standards discussed in this report were prepared in 10L cylinders with BOC SPECTRA-SEAL® passivation.

Table 1, Table 2 and Table 3 provide a summary of the static and dynamic standards used in this study.

Table 1: Static reference material compositions

Component	Gravimetric Amount Fraction $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$		
	D148951	2426	1870
NH3	19.66 \pm 0.03	9.97 \pm 0.01	10.00 \pm 0.01
Methane	Balance	Balance	Balance

Table 2: Dynamic reference material summary 01-10-2024

Parent	Parent Flow (mL/min)	Diluent Flow (mL/min)	Generated Amount Fraction $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$
D148951	6.5	1188	0.1
D148952	10	50	3.3
D148953	25	50	6.6
D148954	13	13	9.8
D148955	17	8	13.4
D148956	42	8	16.5
D148957	25	0	19.7
2426	25	0	10.0

Table 3: Dynamic reference material summary 15-10-2024

Parent	Parent Flow (mL/min)	Diluent Flow (mL/min)	Generated Amount Fraction $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$
D148951	13.5	336	0.8
D148951	6.5	19.5	4.9
D148951	12.5	12.5	9.8
D148951	19.5	6.5	14.7
D148951	25	0	19.7
1870	25	0	10.0

3: Experimental

Dynamic gas standards were generated using an array of thermal mass flow controllers (MFCs). Evenly spaced amount fractions in the range $0.1\text{--}20 \mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ (as per A1.1.1) were generated by mixing a $\sim 20 \mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ static ammonia in methane reference material with pure methane 6.0 from BUSE. The NCD response was recorded for each of the dynamic amount fractions and linear regression was used to characterise detector response as a function of ammonia amount fraction.

Figure 1: Dilution system used to generate dynamic gas standards

Figure 1 shows the dilution system which was used to generate ammonia in biomethane dynamic reference standards for NCD method validation. Pairs of calibrated Bronkhorst MFCs were used to tune reference and diluent gas flows which were then mixed, producing the required amount fraction. Flows below 20% of a controller's nominal flow rate were not used to minimise flow uncertainties. The system was built using SilcoNert® 2000 treated parts to minimise adsorption effects. A total flow of 25 ml/min into the analyser was maintained throughout by venting excess gas through a second piece of tubing.

An existing GC-NCD method was used for the initial validation of D148951. The same method was used to analyse dynamic amount fractions generated by the dilution system in Figure 1:

Table 4: GC method parameters

Instrument	Agilent 8890 gas chromatograph with Agilent 8255 nitrogen chemiluminescence detector
Column	J&W Select Low Ammonia GC column, 3 m, 0.53 mm, with 10 m, 0.25 mm Ultimate Plus restriction
Sample loop volume	0.25 mL
Inlet	Split, 5:1, 10mL/min
Oven method	Original: 60°C 1 min, 60-120°C ramp 4min, Extended: 60°C 1 min, 60-120°C ramp 4min, 120-60°C ramp 2 min
Valve box	100 °C
Carrier gas	Helium, 2 mL/min
Detector	
Base temperature	280 °C
Burner temperature	900 °C
H2 Flow	3 mL/min
Oxidiser flow (O2)	8 mL/min
Data analysis	Agilent OpenLab 3.2.2

4: Linearity

Average peak area was recorded for each of the dynamic amount fractions in Table 2 and Table 3 using a nitrogen chemiluminescence detector. A minimum of 5 repeat runs were averaged for each of the dynamic amount fractions. NPL's XLGENLINE software was used to perform a weighted, linear least squares fit on the data and calculate gradient and y intercept uncertainties. R^2 was calculated to assess goodness of the linear fit for each data set, informing the viable working range for use in the future conformity assessment of biomethane.

Figure 2 and Figure 3 show average NCD peak area for a range of evenly spaced dynamic amount fractions between 0 and 20 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$. Seven evenly spaced dynamic amount fractions were used on the 01-10-2024 and five were used on 15-10-2024. $k=2$ standard uncertainties are indicated by vertical black bars.

The points where the linear fit does not pass through the measurement uncertainties were likely due to loss of ammonia through adsorption to the walls of tubing in the analyser and dilution system. Similarly, measurements of some low-amount-fraction dynamic standards may have been biased by residual ammonia from high-amount-fraction standards which were run shortly before.

If this method is used for the conformity assessment of biomethane then dynamic amount fractions should be given adequate time to stabilise before measurements are made. The high number of repeat readings required in a single day to produce a calibration curve made it impractical to allow a long passivation time for each amount fraction. Further work is required to quantify the passivation time required for readings to stabilise.

Figure 2: 01-10-2024 calibration curve. Cyan point shows static check standard (2426) Error bars show $k=2$ standard uncertainties for a minimum of five repeat peak area measurements.

Figure 3: 15-10-2024 calibration curve. Cyan point shows static check standard (1870) Error bars show $k=2$ standard uncertainties for a minimum of five repeat peak area measurements.

Figure 4 and Figure 5 show the residuals for the linear fits in Figure 2 and Figure 3. Residuals are, for the most part, randomly distributed above and below the fit. The only exceptions being 16.5 and 19.7 $\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ on 01-10-2024 where a region of apparent non-linearity occurred. This is likely due to the adsorption effects mentioned previously, as repeat analysis on 15-10-2024 produced a linear fit with a random distribution of residuals. R^2 values for the fitted data were 0.91 for 01-10-2024 and 0.98 for 15-10-2024.

Figure 4: 01-10-2024 fitted data residuals.

Figure 5: 15-10-2024 fitted data residuals

5: Trueness

The calculated amount fraction of the static ammonia standards (2426 and 1870) evaluated using the calibration curves were compared to the gravimetric value of the PRMs according to Equation 1.

$$\Delta_m = |c_m - c_{ref}| \quad \text{Equation 1}$$

Where:

Δ_m = the absolute difference between the mean measured value and the reference value;

c_m = the mean measured value; and

c_{ref} = the gravimetric standard reference value.

The expanded uncertainty of the difference was determined by the quadrature sum of the uncertainties of the reference value and the measurement results according to Equation 2.

$$U_{\Delta} = 2 \sqrt{u_m^2 + u_{ref}^2} \quad \text{Equation 2}$$

Where:

U_{Δ} = the expanded uncertainty of the absolute difference between the mean measured value and the reference value ($k = 2$);

u_m = the uncertainty of the mean measured value ($k = 1$); and

u_{ref} = the uncertainty of the reference value ($k = 1$).

The expanded ($k = 2$) uncertainty corresponds to a confidence interval of 95%.

If the expanded uncertainty of the difference is smaller than the absolute difference between the mean measured value and the reference value, the difference is considered significant (highlighted red).

Table 5 and Table 6 provide an overview of the trueness of the calibration curves as measured against the static reference standards 2426 and 1870. The calculated amount fraction on 01-10-2024 was an average of 3 repeated measurements and the amount fraction on 15-10-2024 an average of 6.

Fitted data from 01-10-2024 showed good agreement with static standard 2426. Fitted data from 15-10-2024 was used to evaluate the amount fraction of static standard 1870. The difference between calculated and gravimetric amount fractions (shown in red) was not fully accounted for by the expanded uncertainty and is therefore significant.

Table 5: Results of inverse evaluation of static standard 2426. Calculated amount fraction showed good agreement with gravimetric amount fraction.

2426	Ammonia
Gravimetric standard reference value c_{ref} ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	9.97
Uncertainty of the reference value u_{ref} ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.01
Mean measured value c_m ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	9.75
Uncertainty of measured value u_m ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.37
Absolute difference Δ_m ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.22
Expanded uncertainty U_{Δ} ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.74

Table 6: Results of inverse evaluation of static standard 1870. Expanded uncertainty did not account for the difference between calculated and gravimetric amount fractions.

1870	Ammonia
Gravimetric standard reference value c_{ref} ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	10.00
Uncertainty of the reference value u_{ref} ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.01
Mean measured value c_m ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	11.61
Uncertainty of measured value u_m	0.33
Absolute difference Δ_m ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	1.61
Expanded uncertainty U_{Δ} ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0.66

6: Precision

Measurement precision was split into repeatability and intermediate precision to distinguish the uncertainty contribution of the instrument (repeatability) and the uncertainty contribution of day-to-day variation (intermediate precision).

6.1: Repeatability

The repeatability of the measurement method was determined using six consecutive measurements of the static check standard 1870. The repeatability was estimated as the relative standard deviation of GC-NCD peak area.

Table 7: Repeatability

1870	Ammonia
Gravimetric standard reference value ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	10.00
RSD (%)	2.25

6.2 Within-lab reproducibility (intermediate precision)

The difference between the measured and gravimetric values of 1870 exceeded the expanded measurement uncertainty when evaluating trueness. As such, a meaningful estimate of the intermediate precision could not be made.

8: Limit of detection and quantification

The limit of quantification (LOQ) is the minimum amount fraction of an analyte which can be confidently determined using an analytical method. The limit of detection (LOD) refers to the minimum amount fraction of an analyte which can be confidently detected. The BiometCAP protocol (A2.1.4) outlines a procedure for the determination of LOQ and LOD, for a measurement not requiring blank correction:

$$\begin{aligned}
 1. \quad & \text{LOD} = 3 \times s'_0 \\
 & \text{LOQ} = 10 \times s'_0 \\
 & s'_0 = \frac{s_0}{\sqrt{n}}
 \end{aligned}
 \qquad \text{Equation 3}$$

Where:

s_0 is the estimated standard deviation of multiple replicate measurements at or near zero amount fraction.

n is the number of replicate measurements

Standard deviation of peak areas was estimated from the repeat measurements of the dynamic $0.1 \mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ ammonia standard in Table 2. Ammonia LOQ and LOD for the method outlined in Table 4 were estimated using Equation 3, indicating a LOQ of 51.52 pAs and a LOD of 15.45 pAs. This LOQ was cross referenced with the least squares fit in Figure 3, yielding an approximate LOQ of $0.11 \mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$ and corresponding LOD of $0.03 \mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$.

9: Interferences/selectivity

An assessment of likely interferences was made for the acquisition method. Amines were highlighted as a potential source of interference due to their occurrence in biomethane. While amines and ammonia are both detectable by GC-NCD, the difference in boiling points makes them easily separable for the column used with the method. As such, amines are expected to be fully resolved from the ammonia when using this method for biomethane conformity assessment.

10: Uncertainty Budget

The future uncertainty budget for this analytical method may be calculated using Equation 4.

$$U = k \sqrt{u_r^2 + u_{day}^2 + \Delta_m^2} \quad \text{Equation 4}$$

Where:

- U = the expanded uncertainty of the analytical method;
- k = the coverage factor ($k = 2$ for 95% confidence level);
- u_r = the relative uncertainty due to measurement repeatability;
- u_{day} = the relative uncertainty due to day-to-day variations (within-lab reproducibility); and
- Δ_m = the bias of the analytical method.

Table 8: Summary of current uncertainty budget for GC-NCD analytical method.

Repeatability u_r (%)	2.25%
Reproducibility u_{day} (%)	N/A
Analytical bias Δ_m (%)	>10%
Expanded uncertainty U (%)	N/A

11: Conclusion

The evaluation criteria for the validation of the analytical methods using GC-NCD for the quantification of ammonia in biomethane are summarised in Table 9.

Table 9: Summary of performance evaluation criteria for validation of analytical method for quantifying ammonia in biomethane using GC-NCD.

Criterion	Target value	Actual value
Working range ($\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$)	0-20	0.1-19.7
R ² over working range	>0.99	0.91/0.98
LOD (mol mol^{-1})	14.36	0.03
LOQ (mol mol^{-1})	≤ 14.36	0.11
Trueness (%)	< 6.00	>10%
Repeatability (%)	< 6.00	2.25%
Intermediate precision (%)	< 6.00	-
Expanded uncertainty (%)	< 6.00	-

The validation of the method for analysing ammonia in biomethane was performed according to the performance assessment protocol written in A2.1.4 where possible. Not all criteria were met. This is likely a result of purging and passivation effects associated with the sampling system causing bias in the calibration curves. Further work is needed to quantify the passivation time of the dilution system in the proposed working range before this method can be reliably used for the quantification of ammonia for the conformity assessment of biomethane.

REPORT

A2.2.2: Validation of the fitness of purpose of the performance assessment protocol developed in A2.1.4 by demonstrating its applicability for ammonia using laser spectroscopy

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Contents

1. Introduction	3
2. Scope of the validation	3
3. Analytical methods and reference gas standards	4
a. HCl analyzer	4
b. HCl reference gas standards	4
c. NH ₃ analyzer	6
d. NH ₃ reference gases	6
3. NH ₃ results	6
a. Limit of detection and quantification	6
b. Working range	7
c. Linearity	7
d. Selectivity	8
e. Precision	9
f. Measurement uncertainties	10
g. Response time	10
4. HCl results	10
a. Limit of detection and quantification	10
b. Working range	11
c. Linearity	11
d. Precision	12
e. Measurement uncertainties	13
f. Response time	13
5. Applicability of the protocol to hydrogen fluoride	13
6. Conclusions	14
7. References	15

1. Introduction

This report describes the validation of the fitness of purpose of the protocol developed in activity A2.1.4 for the measurement in biomethane using laser spectroscopic techniques operated at VSL. This is done for ammonia (NH₃) as part of activity A2.2.2 and hydrogen chloride (HCl) as part of activity A2.2.3. In addition, the applicability of the protocol to the validation of measurements of hydrogen fluoride (HF) in biomethane will be described (no experimental work will be carried out for HF).

The EN standard EN16723-1:2016 provides specifications for biomethane for injection in the natural gas network. For ammonia, this standard gives an upper limit value of 10 mg/m³ which is equivalent to about 14 μmol/mol at standard reference conditions. For chlorinated compounds (as well as for HF), EN16723-1:2016 does not give a clear upper limit. Instead, it refers to CEN/TR 17238:2018 [4], which gives an approach for assessment of limit values of contaminants in biomethane based on health assessment criteria, modelling and different scenarios, and it does not consider other impacts of these contaminants such as on the integrity of pipelines or appliances. As a result, the limit value for chlorinated compounds is both country-dependent (as health criteria values are typically determined at the national level) and application-specific. Accordingly, corresponding limit values for HCl do vary over a wide range, ranging from a few mg m⁻³ to values exceeding several hundred mg m⁻³ (note 1 mg m⁻³ is approximately 0.67 μmol mol⁻¹ at standard reference conditions). To assess the fitness of purpose of the protocol developed in A2.1.4, for NH₃ it is clear from the EN16723-1 standard what the relevant levels of NH₃ are. For HCl this is not directly evident based on the discussion above. Here we chose to validate the HCl analyzer at the more challenging range of the lower μmol mol⁻¹ down to sub μmol mol⁻¹. Higher amount fractions could be relatively easily measured with the set-up using either dynamic dilution or choosing a measurement cell with a shorter optical path length.

2. Scope of the validation

The extent of the performance characteristic validation for HCl and NH₃ analyzers in biomethane is summarized in Table 10. Here not a full validation has been performed as, in particular for selectivity when one could test all kinds of different matrix compositions which would require very extensive experiments beyond the budget of this project. However, the results described here will provide some insights into how a full validation can be performed.

Table 10 *Extent of validation for HCl and NH₃ analyzers in biomethane. Note that for selectivity only very limited experiments were carried out. A full test would require a test with a much wider range of potential interfering compounds. As both analyzers can be used for on-line analysis, here also the response time is included in the validation.*

Performance characteristic	Component quantification
Selectivity (only for NH ₃)	x
Limit of detection	
Limit of quantification	x
Working range	x
Precision	x
Response time	x

3. Analytical methods and reference gas standards

a. HCl analyzer

The custom-built TDLS spectrometer employs an interband cascade laser (Nanoplus, Germany) with collimator. The laser is used to probe the P6 line of HCl centred at 3633.68 nm (2752.04 cm⁻¹) which has a line strength of S=1.92·10⁻¹⁹ cm/molecule (HITRAN). This line is not the strongest available HCl absorption line in the fundamental ν₁-band of HCl, yet it suffers less from spectral interference by methane as compared to other strong HCl absorption lines [5]. The laser is tuned over the absorption line at a rate of 200 Hz. The laser beam is coupled into a multi-pass cell (Aerodyne, USA) with an effective path length of 76 m (cell volume is 0.5 l) via several silver-coated mirrors and the exiting light is focused using a parabolic mirror on a 2-stage Peltier-cooled detector (PVI-4TE from VIGO, Poland). The pressure in the cell is maintained at 100 mbar using a combination of a pressure controller and a membrane pump. The flow rate through the cell was typically 300 ml/min.

b. HCl reference gas standards

Two different methods were used to prepare HCl reference gas standards in methane at the required amount fractions:

1. Dynamic dilution of a static HCl in CH₄ gas mixture (Figure 6). For the static HCl in CH₄ standard, a commercial mixture was used which had been certified shortly beforehand.

Figure 6 Overview of the experimental set-up used for the dynamic dilution of static HCl in CH₄ and the subsequent measurement by TDLS.

2. Dynamic generation based on permeation following ISO 6145-10 and using a magnetic suspension balance (MSB) as shown in Figure 7. For more details on permeation-based system, see Nwaboh et al., 2021. The permeation tube was obtained from Fine Metrology and had a quoted permeation rate of 600 ng/min at 50°C. Part of the flow is directed to the vent while the flow directed to the analyzer is kept constant at 300 ml/min. Note that the permeation chamber itself is flushed with N₂ while the much larger dilution flow is CH₄, therefore there will always be some N₂ in the matrix gas.

Figure 7 Generation of HCl in CH₄ standards based on permeation following ISO 6145-10 (permeation) and ISO 6145-7 (thermal mass flow controllers).

c. NH₃ analyzer

The analyzer is a custom-built TDLS spectrometer utilizing a mid-infrared quantum-cascade laser (Alpes lasers, Switzerland) as light source. The laser operates in the 9537-9585 nm (1049-1043 cm⁻¹) wavelength range. To measure NH₃, an NH₃ absorption feature centered around 1046.4 cm⁻¹ is used, consisting of various absorption lines with individual line strengths up to $S=3.648 \cdot 10^{-19}$ cm/molecule (HITRAN database). Since the threshold value for NH₃ in EN16723-1 is relatively relaxed (10 mg/m³ or about 14 μmol/mol), a relatively short measurement cell with an optical path length of 3 m (cell volume is 100 ml) was used in this case (note that for HCl a cell with a longer optical path length of 76 m was used as lower HCl amount fractions were targeted). The measurement cell was operated at a pressure of 100 mbar (hence the effective amount of gas inside the cell is only 10 ml). Flow rate through the cell was typically 300 ml/min.

For NH₃ a similar dilution system using mass-flow controllers was used as for HCl. Further also, the magnetic suspension balance was operated using a NH₃ permeation tube (Fine Metrology, Italy) with a specified permeation rate of 3500 ng/min when operated at 30 °C.

d. NH₃ reference gases

Again as for HCl, two different methods were used to prepare NH₃ reference gas standards in methane at the required amount fractions:

- a. Dynamic dilution of a static NH₃ in biogas gas mixture (using a set-up similar as shown for HCl in Figure 6). For the static NH₃ in biogas standard, two different biogas matrices were available.
- b. Permeation based system identical to the system used for HCl. Also here, the permeation tube was obtained from Fine Metrology and had a quoted permeation rate of 600 ng/min at 50°C.

3. NH₃ results

a. Limit of detection and quantification

According to the protocol, the LOD and LOQ can be calculated in one of two ways: via replicate measurements of blank samples, or via replicate measurements of test samples with a suitably low amount fraction of the analyte. Here replicate measurements of blank samples were used and the following equation was used:

$$s'_0 = \frac{s_0}{\sqrt{n}} \quad \text{equation (1)}$$

Where:

- s'_0 the standard deviation used for calculating LOD and LOQ
- s_0 is the estimated standard deviation of 10 single results of blank samples
- n the number of replicate observations averaged when reporting results (here n=10)

Then LOD and LOQ are calculated as follows:

$$\text{LOD} = 3 \times s'_0$$

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times s'_0$$

The LOD and LOQ for NH₃ in CH₄ were determined to be 10 nmol/mol and 34 nmol/mol, respectively.

b. Working range

The lower range of the working range is determined by the LOQ. For the working range we did not investigate the upper range of NH₃ in CH₄ but extensive NH₃ experiments in N₂ have been performed which showed an upper range of 300 μmol/mol. Beyond this level, absorbance by ammonia becomes too strong resulting in a strongly non-linear analyzer response. The upper range for a CH₄ matrix will be nearly identical as for the N₂ matrix since additional absorbance by CH₄ is very low (see next section). Therefore the working range of the analyzer is from around 0.034 μmol/mol to 300 μmol/mol.

c. Linearity

The linearity was assessed by dynamically dilution a NH₃ in biomethane mixture with pure CH₄ (see *Figure 8* for a typical measurement).

The goodness-of-fit value was 0.48 for a first-order linear regression fit. For a satisfactory fit of the data, it was required that the absolute value of the normalized residual was not exceeding 2, and therefore the analyzer can be considered linear over the tested range. The normalized residual is the residual divided by the standard uncertainty. All the normalized residuals were < 2, indicating this function is fit for purpose.

Figure 8 Example of measurement of NH_3 using dynamic dilution with thermal mass flow controllers to assess the linearity of the analyzer.

d. Selectivity

Figure 9 shows a spectral simulation of a low amount fraction of $1 \mu\text{mol/mol}$ NH_3 and compares this to the absorption of high amount fractions of CH_4 (80 % mol/mol) and CO_2 (20 % mol/mol), the main matrix components found in biomethane. From the graph it can be seen that interference due to absorption by these major components is relatively low for NH_3 amount fractions even well below the EN threshold. Another way the matrix compounds can affect the analyzer response is due to a change in the broadening of the NH_3 absorption line. This effect is also relatively minor, as was shown in a previous study [6].

Figure 9 Spectral simulation of a measurement of NH_3 at $1 \mu\text{mol/mol}$ (i.e., about 14 times lower than the EN16723 threshold), CH_4 at 80 cmol/mol and CO_2 at 20 cmol/mol (pressure is 100 mbar and temperature is 20°C). This shows that even at such a low NH_3 ammonia amount fractions, spectral interference by the main biomethane matrix components is relatively low.

To experimentally assess the selectivity of the analyzer, the magnetic suspension balance was used to generate ammonia and the composition of the matrix gas was varied (i.e., the concentrations of nitrogen and methane). Based on the observed changes, it was determined that typical variations of the methane fraction (84% mol/mol – 100% mol/mol) in biomethane lead to changes up to 1% in the analyzed NH_3 amount fraction at the EN16723 threshold value. This confirms the relative insensitivity of the analyzer with regards to CH_4 interference.

e. Precision

Long-term, continuous measurements were carried of NH_3 in CH_4 reference gas mixtures generated using the MSB. As an example, Figure 10 shows part of a measurement carried out $10 \mu\text{mol/mol}$ NH_3 in CH_4 , i.e., just below the EN16723 threshold value.

Figure 10 Example of a long-term measurement of NH_3 generated using the MSB. Short-term precision is good but long-term drifts are visible.

At such an amount fraction, the analyzer response showed peak-to-peak variations up to 2.5% with a small part of this being due to variations in the generated amount fraction by the MSB. The precision was calculated using the pooled standard deviation as a measure of precision of the method. The resulting precision is 0.083 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ at 10 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ NH_3 in CH_4 .

f. Measurement uncertainties

The combined measurement uncertainty of the method was assessed by an empirical approach based upon identification of uncertainty sources as square root of sum of squared quantities of individual sources given in amount fraction units for ammonia measurement.

The uncertainty contributions include the uncertainty of the reference standard, the bias, the precision, and the uncertainty due to variation of the matrix gas. Around the EN15723 threshold value for ammonia, the expanded measurement uncertainty ($k=2$) is 6% relative. This value increases at lower NH_3 amount fractions. The dominant sources are the uncertainty due to the reference standard and the bias. In general, measurement uncertainty of 10% or less are considered reliable.

g. Response time

The response time both from a low amount fraction of NH_3 in CH_4 (0.6 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$) to blank and vice versa were determined (see Figure 8 to get an impression of the analyser time response). Here the t_{90} value was used as the response time. The determined response times were: $T_{90_down} = 260$ seconds and $T_{90_up} = 290$ minutes, respectively. The down response times are, in contrast to HCl (see for those results the next section), comparable in magnitude. This indicated that reactions of NH_3 play a relatively smaller role as compared for the case of HCl. For ammonia, adsorption and desorption effects are the main contributors to the relatively long time response. For comparison, for non-reactive gases using the same cell and sampling system response times of better than 10 seconds can be achieved.

4. HCl results

a. Limit of detection and quantification

The LOD and LOQ were calculated in a similar way as done for ammonia. Here the LOD and LOQ for HCl in CH_4 were determined to be 10 nmol/mol and 33 nmol/mol , respectively.

These values are very similar to those for NH_3 although for HCl a measurement cell with a much longer optical path length (76 m instead of 3 m) was employed. However, the stronger NH_3 absorption (more than twice as strong as HCl for the same amount fraction) and the much stronger spectral interference of CH_4 on the HCl signal as compared to that on the NH_3 signal nullify the benefit of the longer optical path length.

b. Working range

Figure 11 shows a measurement of HCl in methane using dilution of a static mixture with mass flow controllers.

Figure 11 Measurement of HCl in CH₄. Shown are the measurements at 4 second time resolution (—) and the data averaged over 15 datapoints (—), i.e., 1 minute average.

For the working range we did not investigate the upper range in of HCl in CH₄ but this has been determined before for HCl in a N₂ matrix. The maximum amount fraction that can be analysed is around 50 μmol/mol above which the HCl absorbance becomes too strong. For a CH₄ matrix this upper range will be slightly lower due to additional absorbance by CH₄ or the other biomethane matrix components. The lower range is given by the limit of quantification. The working range is therefore around 0.03 to 40 μmol/mol.

c. Linearity

The linearity of the system has been tested over the range of 0.6 μmol/mol to 6 μmol/mol according to ISO 6143. The Goodness-of-fit value was 1.01 for a first order linear regression fit. For a satisfactory fit of the data, it was required that the absolute value of the normalized residual was not exceeding 2. The normalized residual is the residual divided by the standard uncertainty. All the normalized residuals were < 2, indicating this function is fit for purpose.

d. Precision

Long-term, continuous measurements were carried of HCl in CH₄ reference gas mixtures generated using the MSB and further also a static HCl in CH₄ mixture was analysed. As an example, Figure 12 shows part of a measurement carried out.

Figure 12 Long-term measurements of HCl generated using the magnetic suspension balance (data are averaged over 15 data points). Around $t=19$ hours the temperature of the permeation chamber was increased leading to an increase in HCl amount fraction. The generated amount fractions takes nearly 3 hours to stabilize (time due to the generation system, not the analyzer).

As an example, at an amount fraction of 12 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$, the analyzer response showed peak-to-peak variations up to 6% with a small part of this being due to variations in the generated amount fraction by the MSB. The precision was calculated using the pooled standard deviation as a measure of precision of the method. The resulting precision is 0.05 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ at an HCl amount fraction of 12 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$.

e. Measurement uncertainties

As for ammonia, the combined measurement uncertainty of the HCl measurement method was assessed by an empirical approach based upon identification of uncertainty sources as square root of sum of squared quantities of individual sources given in amount fraction units for ammonia measurement.

The uncertainty contributions include the uncertainty of the reference standard, the bias, the precision (the uncertainty due to variation of the matrix gas was not included for HCl). The expanded measurement uncertainty ($k=2$) is 7% relative for measurement of HCl in the lower $\mu\text{mol/mol}$ range. This value increases with decreasing HCl amount fractions. The dominant sources are the uncertainty due to the reference standard and the bias. In general, measurement uncertainty of 10% or less are considered reliable.

f. Response time

The response time both from a low amount fraction of HCl in CH_4 (0.6 $\mu\text{mol/mol}$) to blank and vice versa were determined (see Figure 11 to get an impression of the analyser time response). Here the t_{90} value was used as the response time. The determined response times were: $T_{90_down} = 50$ seconds, $T_{90_up} = 8$ minutes. The down response time is nearly 10 times faster than the up response time indicating that likely reactions of HCl with the sampling system do occur.

5. Applicability of the protocol to hydrogen fluoride

For hydrogen fluoride (HF), VSL operates a similar TDLS system as used for NH_3 and HCl. A key difference lies however in the used materials as HF reacts with glass-like materials. Examples of such materials are SilcoNert coatings but also the glass chamber of a magnetic suspension balance or the glass tube of the multi-pass cell used for the HCl measurements. It has been shown at VSL that the reaction of HF with such glass materials leads to the formation of SiF_4 (Silicon tetrafluoride) and thus a decrease of the HF amount fraction. Therefore, uncoated mass flow controllers, uncoated pressure controllers and uncoated tubings need to be used (i.e., materials exposed to HF will be mostly stainless steel while tubings can also be polymer-based). For the HF measurement a custom-made Polyacetal cell is used to prevent reactions of HF with the measurement cell. Further, it is advised to keep the system dry.

The TDLS system operated at VSL uses a wavelength of 2475.88 nm (4038.96 cm^{-1}) with a good sensitivity down to the nmol/mol level 0. Figure 13 shows a simulation of the HF absorption in the presence of CH_4 and CO_2 . CH_4 is the dominant interfering species while CO_2 interference is minimal. Other gases which might be present in biomethane and for which interference is negligible are H_2O , CO , and HCl while interference for NH_3 is low. Note that for other optical analysers operating at different wavelengths, the levels of interference can be completely different.

Figure 13 Simulation of the absorption by HF ($1\text{ }\mu\text{mol/mol}$) in the presence of CH_4 (80 cmol/mol) and CO_2 (20 cmol/mol) at a pressure of 0.1 bar absolute and temperature of 293 K.

In general, the protocol will be applicable to HF, but as noted before, the choice of materials requires special attention for the analysis of HF.

6. Conclusions

Within this report the suitability of the protocol developed in A2.1.4 was determined for TDLS analyzers for HCl in biomethane and NH_3 in biomethane analysis.

Most parts of the protocol are fit for purpose, while some other parts should be more specific. As an example of the latter, the interference testing is not specified in detail. This leaves it more or less open to the user how many interferences and at which level the testing will be done, how it needs to be reported, and what are acceptable levels of interference. Uncertainty contributions due to variations in the biomethane matrix compositions can be large for spectroscopic analyzers, but a full assessment of this uncertainty contribution is a lot of work due to the complexity of the biomethane matrix.

Another point which has already been made in the introduction is that for some compounds like HCl , the EN16723-1:2016 standard does not provide clear limit values but instead refers to CEN/TR 17238:2018. This standard gives an approach for assessment of limit values of contaminants in biomethane based on health assessment criteria, modelling and different scenarios. As a result, when an analyzer for a compound such as HCl has been validated for one country, it may require new validation experiments for other countries with different limit values.

7. References

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